

Welcome Note and Future Directions of IJDAS

Dhurjati Majumdar¹ and Anirban Chowdhury²

¹Former Scientist G and Associate Director, Defence Research and Development Organisation (DRDO), India

² School of Design (SoD), University of Petroleum and Energy Studies (UPES), Dehradun-248007, Uttarakhand, India

1. Introduction

The International Journal of Design and Allied Sciences (IJDAS) is a multidisciplinary peer-reviewed open-access journal (however, print version shall be sent to the author(s) or library on-demand). This journal focuses on all art, design, allied sciences (e.g. human factors, ergonomics, and work physiology), engineering, and technologies. Readership of this journal includes students, academicians, industry experts, and aspirants of art, design, and allied sciences. This journal also publishes short industry case studies, graphic novels, and short videographic materials or documentaries on various processes and design methods with concept notes, art and craft materials with concept notes, and commentary from academic and industry experts. This journal is committed to publishing 2 issues in a year. Typically, the first review comes within a week after submission, and the minimum publication time is 5-8 weeks.

“ We Believe that Everyone is Creative, Just Need to Nurture and Develop Creative Mindset !!!”

(A Righ Balance between Imagination and Analytical Skill is Very Important for any Creative Problem Solving)

Are You A Problem Solver / Creative Professional?

Kindly Contribute for IJDAS

Typical Submission Types

- Very Short Article/ Commentary or Review on Design or Technology (minimum 1000 words)
- Short Original Articles/ Industrial Case Studies (2000-3000 words)
- Full Length Original/Review Article (5000-7000 words)
- Videographic Article (maximum 10 min edited video with concept notes of 500 words)
- Graphic Novels (5-15 A4 pages)
- Etc.

Current and future focus areas include –

Design Research Methods I New Materials & Design I Design for Sustainable and Renewable Energy I Design for Safety and Disaster Management I Design for Agriculture I User Experience Design I Usability Engineering I Product Design I Branding and Graphic Design I Performing Art I Art & Craft I Film and Video I Animation and VFX I Fashion and Apparel Design I Design and Culture I Human Anthropology & Design I Retail Design I Service Experience Design I New Media Design I Human-Computer Interaction I Design Economics & Business I Design Thinking and Innovation I Game Design I AI and Design I Cognitive and Affective Computing I CAD & Engineering Design I Mobility and Transportation System Design I Smart Cities & Urban Design I Education Technologies I Design Education I User-Centred Approach to the Internet of Things (IoT) I Defense Allied Sciences I Data Sciences I Decision Sciences I Biomedical Instruments & Interface Design I Behavioural Sciences I Robotics and Automation I Work Physiology and Job Design I

Email corresponding Author: editor.ijdas@gmail.com I Vol. 1 Issue 1 pp. i-ii

Cite as – Majumdar, D. and Chowdhury, A. (2022). Welcome Note and Future Directions of IJDAS. *International Journal of Design and Allied Sciences*, 1 (1), i-ii.

Industry 5.0 and Human Productivity I Sustainability & Circular Economy I Design Management I Design for Social Need I Design for Special Needs and Assistive Technologies I Design for Elderly and Aging I Neurodesign and Neuromarketing I Computational Cognitive Science I Design & Entrepreneurship I Operational Art etc. but not limited to abovementioned areas.

We welcome all editorial board members and authors for submission of their articles via the journal website (<http://www.dronaseeker.co.in/about-ijdas/>)